

**INTERACTIVE VIDEO-BASED LEARNING ON LEAST LEARNED
COMPETENCIES IN MATHEMATICS OF GRADE 8
STUDENTS USING EDPUZZLE: A BASIS FOR
AN ONLINE INTERVENTION**

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Interactive Video-Based Learning on Least Learned Competencies in Mathematics of Grade 8 Students Using Edpuzzle: A Basis for an Online Intervention

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Abstract

This study examined the effectiveness of an Edpuzzle-based interactive video intervention as a potential online learning strategy for addressing the least learned competencies in Grade 8 mathematics at one of the secondary schools in the province of Sorsogon. Using a mixed-method research design with a pretest-posttest control group, the study compared outcomes for an experimental group exposed to the Edpuzzle intervention and a control group taught through traditional methods, followed by a structured interview discussion with 10 students from the experimental group. Sixty students, equally divided into control and experimental groups, were assessed on competencies, including factoring polynomials, simplifying rational expressions, and solving equations and inequalities in two variables. Pretest results showed both groups at a "Needs Improvement" level, with mean scores of 58.1 and 59.1 for the control and experimental groups, respectively. After the intervention, the control group's posttest mean rose modestly to 64.9, reaching a "Fairly Satisfactory" level, indicating slight improvement through traditional instruction. In contrast, the experimental group demonstrated a significant increase, with a posttest mean of 84.3, classified as "Very Satisfactory." This substantial improvement suggests that the Edpuzzle-based intervention was highly effective in enhancing students' understanding of the targeted competencies. Statistical analysis using a t-test for independent samples confirmed a significant difference between the posttest scores of the two groups, while a paired t-test for the experimental group indicated a notable pretest-to-posttest improvement. Qualitative feedback that was thematically analyzed from the experimental group highlighted increased engagement and perceived benefits from the interactive learning format. These findings underscore the potential of Edpuzzle as an online instructional tool for addressing mathematical challenges, suggesting that integrating interactive video-based learning can serve as an effective online intervention to enhance student performance in mathematics. The study advocates for broader use of technology-enhanced interventions in educational settings to improve competency in complex subjects.

Keywords: *interactive video-based learning, edpuzzle, mathematics intervention, least learned competencies, online learning tools*

Introduction

Mathematics is among the core foundation subjects in education and, more importantly, builds a child's critical thinking, problem-solving, and logical reasoning. Nevertheless, despite mathematics' importance and the apparent importance it has been given in educational circles, many children worldwide still fail to achieve success in at least one aspect of mathematics. Indeed, problems in mathematics learning are now even a global issue, especially when the level of focus is in middle school. A statistical study by Mullis et al. (2020) conducted during the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) reflects an enormous proportion of underachievement in mathematics core areas among students dwelling in developed and developing economies. For example, in the United States, it was found that only 33% of the students in the country were at the proficiency level in mathematics during the 2019 National Assessment of Educational Progress (NAEP) (National Center for Education Statistics, 2019). Similar trends have also been seen in Europe, wherein studies show that mathematical competencies are also in decline (European Commission, 2018). In Asia, more specifically in the Philippines, the problem appears to be worse. The Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018 results found Filipino students at the bottom in terms of mathematics performance among 79 countries participating in the survey (OECD, 2019).

At the national level, the Department of Education in the Philippines has been aware for years that its performance in mathematics was poor. Indeed, the Philippine education system has a poor record of enhancing and improving the mastery of students' mathematical competencies over the decades, specifically for middle school learners. The K to 12 curriculum of the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10533) was conceptualized with a specific aim: that is, to enhance student competencies in several subjects, of which mathematics is an example. Meanwhile, the performance of Grade 8 students in mathematics remained an alarming situation, based on other national assessments and even reports from DepEd (2020). These are supported by studies as many Filipino students remain to be poor in foundational mathematics skills (Chinn, 2016). Educational interventions must therefore become the spotlight answer to these challenges, especially in mathematics where the least learned competencies remain for Grade 8 students at a critical stage of learning.

Despite the growing body of research on mathematics education, much of the literature available is not connected to interactive video-based learning tools with specific mathematical deficiencies that students exhibit. Most of the research done on technology-enhanced learning focuses on the very general applications of digital tools in education, like flipped classrooms or blended learning environments. However, very few of these studies have used Edpuzzle, an application through which interactive quizzes can be integrated into video

lessons, to tackle specific mathematical competencies. For instance, although Cherrett et al. (2009) showed the effectiveness of video-based learning as a means of enhancing overall understanding, limited research exists on how such strategies could specifically address students' current gaps in their learning of mathematics. In addition, a study by Özdemir and Akpınar (2018) discusses the advantages of interactive video in terms of student engagement and retention. Nevertheless, little research on its ability to help in improvements in learning outcomes of students in mathematics for middle school students.

The uniqueness of the present study lies in being an outlier to past ones conducted to aim to enhance Grade 8 students' mathematics least learned competencies, using Edpuzzle as an online intervention tool, deviating from the traditional intervention materials. There has been prior research into video-based learning, but the specific focus of this essay is the front-line application of interactive videos aimed at mathematical weaknesses identified through assessment. The research by Chiu (2020) into personalized learning and integration of technology into classrooms lends support to the concept of tailored intervention as having a broad impact on the outcomes of learning. Building on this idea, this research will provide a more precise approach with interactive videos that will interactively engage students with tailored content and allow them to practice and master their competencies in areas where they feel they are the weakest. This approach is also expected to deliver focused remediation that will be much more effective than traditional teaching methods or generalized digital learning platforms.

This is because several strong reasons drove the decision to focus on this problem. In the first place, the researcher found that many Grade 8 students, especially in mathematics, experience extreme difficulties in solving core concepts deficiency that might pay a long-term price for those pupils' overall performance and future options. In the second place, the huge potential of technology in education, particularly interactive video-based platforms like Edpuzzle, is underutilized in the local context. This study attempts to find a novel solution for an age-old problem by integrating those technologies into the classroom. Finally, as the researcher is interested in improving the math outcome for students, it is crucial to provide any information or contribute toward helping develop evidence-based intervention programs adopted by schools all over the country.

The research is grounded on legal and policy directions, especially on this point: that there should be an emphasis on quality education and that technology should be integrated into teaching and learning. Article XIV, Section 1 of the Philippine Constitution, states: "The state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels." Furthermore, Republic Act No. 10533 or Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 sets as a necessity and a mandate for the improvement of student learning outcomes through the introduction of the K to 12 curriculum with innovative teaching methods and technologies. This research resonates with the court pronouncements when it presents an intervention program using interactive video-based learning to upgrade students' mathematical competencies.

In the end, the study aims to fill such a critical gap in the literature by helping determine whether Edpuzzle is an effective tool for addressing the least learned competencies in mathematics among Grade 8 students. Focusing on a targeted intervention and furnishing a basis for a comprehensive program, the study will contribute to the efforts to make the mathematics educational delivery better at every local, national, and global level.

Research Questions

The main goal of this study is to evaluate the learning effectiveness of Edpuzzle as an interactive video to respond to the least learned competencies of Grade 8 students of one of the secondary schools in the province of Sorsogon in the School Year 2023 – 2024 in the subject mathematics. More specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the pretest and posttest scores of the controlled and experimental groups on the least learned competencies in Grade 8 Mathematics?
2. Is there a significant difference between the posttest scores of the controlled and experimental groups, and between the pretest and posttest scores of the experimental group?
3. What are the experiences, impressions and attitudes of the experimental group towards Edpuzzle in enhancing their knowledge of their least learned topics in Mathematics 8, incorporating engagement and motivation, and learning improvement?
4. What proposal for the online intervention program for mathematics education in schools shall be created using interactive video-based learning tools such as Edpuzzle to fill out the targeted learning gaps based on the findings of the study?

Literature Review

Interactive video-based learning has emerged as a significant pedagogical approach in mathematics education, offering dynamic and engaging content that enhances student understanding and retention. The integration of interactive elements within video lessons allows learners to actively engage with mathematical concepts actively, facilitating deeper comprehension.

A study by Ghilay (2021) examined the effectiveness of text-based video (TBV) models in higher education mathematics courses. The research found that combining high-quality texts with corresponding video clips improved student learning outcomes, particularly in quantitative subjects. The TBV model's flexibility and adaptability to various learning formats, including face-to-face, distance, and blended learning, were highlighted as key benefits.

In the context of K-12 education, Hussein et al. (2022) conducted a systematic literature review on digital game-based learning (DGBL) in mathematics. The review revealed that DGBL applications positively impact knowledge acquisition, cognitive skills, and affective outcomes in mathematics education. Incorporating interactive video elements within educational games was identified as contributing to increased student motivation and engagement.

Furthermore, Huang et al. (2020) explored the use of interest-driven video creation activities in mathematics learning. The study demonstrated that engaging students in creating tutorial videos on mathematical problem-solving not only enhanced their understanding of mathematical concepts but also improved their communication and teamwork skills. This approach aligns with the principles of interactive video-based learning by promoting active participation and collaboration among learners.

The advancement of video technology in education has been accelerated due to the widespread use of portable devices and the increase in internet accessibility. Online learning videos, due to their various positive effects, are becoming increasingly acceptable for both students and teachers. In addition to supporting students in learning, video-based learning also assists teachers in delivering content more effectively (Sablić et al., 2020).

In the Philippines, the integration of interactive video-based learning in mathematics education has been explored to enhance student engagement and address learning gaps, particularly in the context of remote learning necessitated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Nabayra (2021) investigated the development of YouTube-based teacher-created videos for online mathematics learning. The study found that these videos were comprehensive, flexible, and student-friendly, effectively fitting the new normal learning environment. The virtual presence of the teacher in the videos contributed to a more interactive and engaging learning experience for students.

Similarly, Rellama et al. (2023) developed video learning lessons focusing on basic fundamental operations using visual patterns in numeracy education. The study highlighted that incorporating visual learning concepts through video lessons can significantly enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics, especially in blended and remote learning contexts.

Insorio and Macandog (2022) examined the use of video lessons via a YouTube channel as interventions in modular distance learning for Grade 7 mathematics. The study revealed that teacher-made video lessons helped students understand mathematical concepts better, complementing the lessons in the modules. Students reported enjoying the videos, as they provided clear explanations and allowed them to see the teacher's demonstrations.

Edpuzzle is an educational platform that enables educators to transform existing videos into interactive lessons by embedding questions, comments, and assessments directly into the video content. This interactivity promotes active learning and allows for real-time feedback, which is particularly beneficial in mathematics education.

A study by Di Cesare et al. (2021) examined the impact of Edpuzzle-assisted interactive video media on students' interest and motivation in learning mathematics. The findings indicated that the use of Edpuzzle significantly increased student engagement and motivation, leading to improved learning outcomes in mathematics. Furthermore, Edpuzzle's analytics feature provides educators with insights into student performance, enabling them to identify areas where students struggle and tailor instruction accordingly. This data-driven approach facilitates personalized learning experiences, which are essential for addressing diverse student needs in mathematics education.

A study by Sartika et al. (2023) investigated the impact of Edpuzzle-assisted interactive video media on students' interest and motivation in learning mathematics. The findings indicated that the use of Edpuzzle significantly increased student engagement and motivation, suggesting that interactive video media can be an effective tool in mathematics instruction.

Furthermore, Edpuzzle's integration with other educational tools, such as talkSTEM videos, has been explored to engage mathematics students in school. By combining Edpuzzle's interactive features with talkSTEM's real-world math videos, educators can create engaging lessons that connect mathematical concepts to real-life applications, thereby enhancing student understanding and interest in the subject (Dhingra, 2020).

Methodology

Research Design

The present study employed a mixed-method research design to provide a comprehensive analysis of the intervention's effectiveness. This approach integrated both quantitative and qualitative data to measure the effectiveness of interactive video-based learning on students' mastery of specific mathematics competencies while exploring students' experiences with this innovative learning method.

The quantitative component of the study aimed to evaluate the extent of improvement in students' understanding of least learned competencies in Mathematics 8 subject, consisting of factors completely different types of polynomials, simplifying rational algebraic expressions, performing operations on rational algebraic expressions, solving problems involving rational algebraic expressions, solves problems involving linear equations in two variables, solves problems involving systems of linear equations in two variables by (a) graphing; (b) substitution; (c) elimination, and solves problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables. This component involved the use of pre-tests and post-tests, where students completed assessments before and after the intervention. By

comparing pre-test and post-test scores, the study sought to quantify the intervention's effect on students' academic performance in these areas. A paired t-test was employed to determine the statistical significance of any observed improvements. The sample consisted of Grade 8 students who had been identified as needing support in these competencies. The teacher-constructed assessment were aligned with curriculum standards to ensure the validity of the results.

The qualitative component provided a deeper exploration of students' experiences and perceptions of the Edpuzzle-based intervention. Through structured interviews, students had the opportunity to express how Edpuzzle's interactive features—such as embedded questions, immediate feedback, and replay options—had influenced their engagement, understanding, and motivation in learning mathematics. Teachers were also interviewed to provide insights into the challenges and improvements observed among students during the intervention period. This qualitative data was analyzed using thematic analysis, aiming to identify recurring themes and patterns that revealed the factors influencing students' engagement and motivation.

The integration of quantitative and qualitative data followed a sequential explanatory design. Quantitative results were analyzed first to assess the intervention's effectiveness, followed by qualitative analysis to contextualize these findings. This mixed-method approach was essential for understanding not only the measurable outcomes of Edpuzzle on student performance but also the subjective experiences that influenced engagement and motivation. While quantitative data provided statistical evidence of learning gains, qualitative data offered rich insights into how and why these gains occurred. By combining both perspectives, this research design enabled the development of an evidence-based online intervention tailored to the needs of Grade 8 students facing challenges in foundational mathematics skills, ultimately informing future digital interventions aimed at enhancing student achievement in mathematics.

Participants

The research participants consisted of Grade 8 students from one of the secondary schools in the province of Sorsogon during the School Year 2023–2024. A total of 60 students were purposively selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure relevant data for the study. Inclusion criteria required students to have demonstrated below-average performance in a diagnostic mathematics test administered by the school at the start of the academic year, identifying them as needing additional support in mathematics as they struggle in the least learned competencies. Students were also required to be present for the entire intervention period to maintain consistency in exposure to the instructional methods.

Exclusion criteria involved excluding students who had previously shown proficiency in the identified least-learned competencies were omitted, as their participation could potentially skew the measurement of the intervention's impact. This selection process resulted in 30 students assigned to the experimental group, which received the Edpuzzle-based intervention, and 30 students in the control group, which followed the traditional instructional modality. Informed consent was obtained from all participants and their parents, ensuring adherence to ethical guidelines established for the study. Furthermore, 10 students are chosen from the experimental group to be included in the structured interview.

Instrument

The instrument utilized in this study was a set of pretest and posttest assessments designed to measure the least learned mathematical competencies of Grade 8 students before and after the intervention. The items on these assessments were specifically crafted to align with the mentioned competencies outlined by the Department of Education (DepEd) for Grade 8 mathematics. These least learned competencies included factoring different types of polynomials, simplifying rational algebraic expressions, performing operations on rational algebraic expressions, and solving problems involving rational algebraic expressions. Additional focus areas included solving problems involving linear equations in two variables, and systems of linear equations in two variables through graphing, substitution, and elimination methods, as well as solving systems of linear inequalities in two variables.

The assessment items were subjected to a validation process carried out by a panel of mathematics experts. This validation ensured that each item accurately reflected the targeted competencies and was both relevant and challenging for Grade 8 students. Furthermore, a reliability test was conducted on the assessment to confirm the consistency and dependability of the results. The assessments were created to capture an accurate baseline (pretest) of each student's competencies and to measure any improvements following the intervention (posttest). This instrument served as a vital tool for evaluating the effectiveness of the Edpuzzle-based interactive video learning intervention on the least learned competencies in mathematics.

For the interactive video lessons, a series of instructional videos was developed, incorporating quizzes and interactive questions to facilitate active learning. These videos were created by mathematics educators and instructional designers, aligning the content with the curriculum and designed specifically to address the identified areas of difficulty. Before implementation, these videos underwent validation by a panel of experts to guarantee that they were appropriate for the student's grade level and learning needs and that they effectively promoted engagement and understanding of the targeted competencies.

In addition to these assessment tools, a survey was conducted to collect qualitative feedback from the experimental group regarding their experiences with the Edpuzzle intervention. This survey gathered students' opinions on their engagement with the video lessons, the perceived impact on their learning, and any improvements in their understanding of mathematical concepts. Responses were

thematically analyzed, coded, and grouped to provide insights into students' perceptions of the intervention, enhancing the understanding of its overall impact on their learning experience.

Procedure

The study followed a structured procedure designed to assess the effectiveness of the Edpuzzle-based intervention on students' mathematical competencies. Initially, a pretest was administered to both the experimental and control groups to establish a baseline understanding of the least learned competencies in mathematics. This pretest specifically assessed students' abilities in areas such as factoring different types of polynomials, simplifying and performing operations on rational algebraic expressions, and solving problems involving linear equations, systems of equations, and systems of inequalities.

Following the pretest, the experimental group received the intervention through interactive video lessons developed using Edpuzzle, while the control group continued with traditional instructional methods. The Edpuzzle videos, which were created in collaboration with mathematics educators and instructional designers, focused on the identified areas of difficulty. The videos included interactive quizzes and questions embedded within the content to foster active engagement and real-time assessment. These video lessons were validated by a panel of experts to ensure their instructional quality and alignment with the curriculum standards.

After the intervention period, a posttest identical to the pretest was administered to both groups to evaluate any changes in competency levels. Data from the pretest and posttest were analyzed using descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation, to summarize the results. Additionally, a t-test for independent samples was conducted to compare the posttest scores of the two groups, determining if a statistically significant difference existed between them. For the experimental group, a paired t-test was also performed to assess improvements from pretest to posttest. Furthermore, a survey was conducted among the experimental group to gather qualitative insights on their experiences with the Edpuzzle intervention. Responses were then analyzed through thematic coding, revealing students' perspectives on the engagement, effectiveness, and perceived impact of the video-based learning intervention on their understanding of mathematical concepts.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were rigorously observed throughout the study to ensure the rights, well-being, and informed consent of all participants. Given that the subjects were minors, special care was taken to obtain permission not only from the students but also from their parents or guardians. Before the study commenced, detailed information was provided to both students and parents, explaining the objectives, procedures, and potential benefits and risks associated with participation in the research. Informed consent forms were distributed and signed to confirm that all participants and their guardians understood the study's nature and voluntarily agreed to take part.

Confidentiality and privacy were prioritized by anonymizing student data throughout the data collection, analysis, and reporting processes. Personal identifiers were removed, and each participant was assigned a code to ensure that individual responses and test results could not be traced back to specific students. Only the research team had access to the raw data, and all information was stored securely to prevent unauthorized access.

Additionally, the study's design was structured to avoid any undue harm or disruption to the student's regular academic activities. The Edpuzzle intervention was integrated into their curriculum in a way that complemented their existing learning environment without adding excessive workload or pressure. Any student who wished to withdraw from the study at any point was allowed to do so without any academic or personal consequences. This approach aligned with ethical guidelines to safeguard participants' autonomy and protect their educational experience.

Results and Discussion

Pretest and Posttest Scores of the Controlled and Experimental Group

The table below shows the mean scores, standard deviations, and interpretations of the pretest and posttest scores for both the experimental and control groups of this study.

Table 1. *Descriptive Statistics of Pretest and Posttest Scores for Experimental and Control Groups*

Group	Type of Test	Mean	Standard Deviation	Description
Control	Pretest	58.1	5.46	Needs Improvement
	Posttest	64.9	5.45	Fairly Satisfactory
Experimental	Pretest	59.1	4.50	Needs Improvement
	Posttest	84.3	5.59	Very Satisfactory

Note: Below 50 = Poor; 50 – 59 = Needs Improvement; 60 – 69 = Fairly Satisfactory; 70 – 79 = Satisfactory; 80 – 89 = Very Satisfactory; 90 – 100 = Outstanding

In the control group, the mean score on the pretest was 58.1 with a standard deviation of 5.46, categorized as "Needs Improvement." This indicates that, on average, students in the control group had a limited understanding of the targeted competencies before any intervention. After undergoing traditional instructional methods, the control group's posttest mean increased to 64.9, with a standard

deviation of 5.45, moving the performance level to "Fairly Satisfactory." This modest improvement suggests that traditional instruction had a positive but limited impact on the students' competencies, as they moved from needing improvement to a basic level of understanding.

The experimental group, which received the Edpuzzle-based intervention, showed a pretest mean of 59.1 with a standard deviation of 4.50, also categorized as "Needs Improvement." This starting point was similar to the control group, indicating comparable baseline competencies. However, the posttest mean in the experimental group rose significantly to 84.3, with a standard deviation of 5.59, moving the performance level to "Very Satisfactory." This substantial increase indicates that the interactive video-based learning intervention through Edpuzzle was highly effective, helping students achieve a strong understanding of the competencies. The experimental group's shift to "Very Satisfactory" highlights the success of the Edpuzzle intervention in enhancing student comprehension and performance.

Effectiveness of Edpuzzle on Enhancing Least Learned Competencies in Grade 8 Mathematics

To verify whether there was any statistically significant difference between the posttest scores of the control and experimental groups and to check the significance of improvement in the experimental group, two types of t-tests were conducted: Independent Samples t-test comparing the posttest scores between the control and experimental groups and Paired Samples t-test comparing pretest and posttest scores between experimental group subjects.

Table 2. Independent Samples t-test for post-test scores of Control and Experimental Groups

Group	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Sig. Value	Interpretation	Decision to Null
Control	64.9	5.45	-13.36	<001	Significant	Reject
Experimental	84.3	5.59				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

From the table, the t-test results would imply that there was an existence of a difference between control and experimental posttest scores, which was statistically significant, with a t-value of -13.36 and p-value < 0.001. The mean score for the posttest of the experimental group is significantly higher at 84.3 than that for the control group, which is at 64.9. This hence confirms that the intervention using Edpuzzle had a positive effect on the performance of the experimental group. As the value of p is smaller than the pre-set level of significance of 0.05, we negate the null hypothesis. This instead means that there is a statistically significant difference in the posttest scores between both groups.

Table 3. Paired t-test results for Pretest and Posttest Scores of Experimental Group

Type of Test	Mean	Standard Deviation	t-value	Sig. Value	Interpretation	Decision to Null
Pretest	59.1	4.50	-20.2	<001	Significant	Reject
Posttest	84.3	5.59				

$\alpha = 0.05$ Level of Significance

The paired t-test results from table 3 report a t-value of -20.2 and a p-value < 0.001. This means that indeed, there is a statistically significant improvement in scores for the experimental group from the pretest to the posttest. Scores rose from 59.1 (Poor) to 84.3 (Satisfactory), indicating that because of the Edpuzzle intervention, remarkable improvements existed.

Since the p-value is less than the selected significance level of 0.05, we deny the null hypothesis. This means there is a statistically significant performance improvement in the experimental group following the intervention. In conclusion, the analysis yields strong evidence that the interactive video-based learning intervention with Edpuzzle had brought out significant and appreciated improvements in the performance of the students.

Several studies support the findings of this research, indicating that the use of Edpuzzle in educational interventions leads to statistically significant improvements in student performance. For instance, Tshering, Wangchuk, and Dorji (2022) explored the use of Edpuzzle videos in a Grade 9 Biology class and found a significant increase in posttest scores compared to the pretest scores. This aligns with the current research, which also demonstrated a notable improvement in the experimental group's performance following the Edpuzzle intervention.

Similarly, Akdoğdu, Demir, and Aksu-Dünya (2022) assessed the use of Edpuzzle in an assessment and measurement course, finding a statistically significant difference in the posttest scores of the experimental group compared to the control group. Additionally, Khalil, Al-Maawali, and El-Ghool (2022) found that quiz-based interactive videos using Edpuzzle significantly improved student performance after the intervention, corroborating the positive effect of Edpuzzle observed in this study.

However, some studies present contrasting results. For example, Elliott (2019) conducted a study on English Language Learners using Edpuzzle and found no statistically significant difference between the posttest scores of the experimental and control groups, which contradicts the findings of this research. Similarly, Ayçiçek and Yanpar Yelken (2018) reported that while there was an improvement in the experimental group's scores, the difference between the experimental and control groups was less pronounced than in the current study. These contrasting findings suggest that while Edpuzzle can be an effective educational tool, its success may vary based on factors such as subject matter, student demographics, and implementation methods.

Exploring the Attitudes of the Experimental Group towards Edpuzzle

This section includes a thematic analysis, based on the structured interview responses, to solicit attitudes from the students in the experimental group about the application of Edpuzzle in building their knowledge on the least learned topics in Mathematics 8, in support of the quantitative results.

Table 4. *Thematic Analysis of Student Responses to Edpuzzle Use*

<i>Condensed Meaning Unit</i>	<i>Codes</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Themes</i>
I would say that I enjoyed using Edpuzzle, where videos are interesting and keep attention. I enjoyed it, interesting and kept my attention.	Enjoyed, interesting, attention	Student Engagement	Engagement through Interactive Learning
The questions during the video helped me stay focused and think about the topic more.	Stay focused, think about topic	Cognitive Engagement	Engagement through Interactive Learning
It was fun learning at Edpuzzle since I could answer questions simultaneously while watching.	Fun, answer questions, learning	Enjoyment of Learning	Increased Motivation through Fun Learning
I liked that I could pause the video and replay it when I didn't understand something.	Replay, pause, better understanding	Autonomy in Learning	Autonomy and Personalized Learning
I felt more motivated to study because the videos made math easier to understand.	Motivated, easier to understand	Motivation for Learning	Increased Motivation through Fun Learning
The interactive questions made me realize what I didn't understand and where I needed to improve.	Identify gaps, improve	Self-Assessment and Reflection	Learning Improvement through Immediate Feedback
"I found it helpful that I could see my mistakes right away and learn from them.	Mistakes, learn from mistakes	Immediate Feedback	Learning Improvement through Immediate Feedback
"Math felt less boring with the videos, and I was able to practice what I learned right away.	Less boring, practice right away	Learning Engagement	Increased Motivation through Fun Learning
The videos were short and clear, so it was easier to understand complicated topics.	Short videos, clear explanation	Clarity of Learning Content	Learning Improvement through Simplified Content
Edpuzzle made math more interesting for me, and I felt more confident answering problems.	More interesting, confident	Confidence in Learning	Learning Improvement through Engagement

An in-depth thematic analysis of the students' responses shows a range of positive experiences with Edpuzzle while engaging participants to learn mathematics with more improvements relative to engagement and motivation. The analysis is structured according to four major themes: Engagement through Interactive Learning, Increased Motivation through Fun Learning, Autonomy and Personalized Learning, and Learning Improvement through Immediate Feedback and Simplified Content. Edpuzzle provided an effective learning environment as a motivational, engaging, and attractive site for Grade 8 students who were struggling in mathematics. Students emphasized the more interactive learning is essential to enhancing knowledge but also building self-confidence through fun engagements with autonomy and feedback in real time. For these purposes, all the features came together to create a personalized, effective learning experience that could produce tangible improvements in learning.

Proposal for an Online Intervention for Grade 8 Mathematics

Based on the results of the study, an online intervention program has been proposed to help solve learning gaps in mathematics among students and put emphasis on least learned competencies. These competencies are the following: factors completely different types of polynomials, simplifies rational algebraic expressions, performs operations on rational algebraic expressions, solves problems involving rational algebraic expressions, solves problems involving linear equations in two variables, solves problems involving systems of linear equations in two variables by (a) graphing; (b) substitution; (c) elimination, and solves problems involving systems of linear inequalities in two variables. Such learning gaps-in this case, in foundational areas like algebraic expressions, linear equations, and geometry-may negatively influence general progress throughout every student's academic. By offering students the opportunity to engage in interactive video-based learning with tools such as Edpuzzle, this proposed intervention aims to create a motivating and effective learning experience for mastery of these competencies.

More specific objectives of the program are targeting and addressing specific gaps in learning in mathematics through delivering lessons with Edpuzzle, which pools interactive quizzes into video lessons. That would enhance the students' motivation and active participation by using interesting elements and live feedback, which means that it would encourage the active presence of the students in the process. The intervention should quantify and track improvement in student performance by assessment before the intervention and then after the intervention while offering data-driven insights for instruction to the teachers and support personalized for students who need it most.

The program involves Grade 8 students who, through diagnostic assessments, have critical learning gaps in mathematics in the least learned competencies. The intervention will be fully online and delivered via the Edpuzzle software platform. Teachers will create video lessons targeting the least learned competency items. In addition to videos, quizzes will be embedded so that students may test their understanding immediately in real-time, with immediate feedback on their answers. This keeps the students engaged and allows them to correct misconceptions as they progress through the lessons.

Flexibility is one of the above features of the online intervention provided for the students is a kind of flexibility offered. They can pause, replay, and revisit lessons at their convenience to provide a personalized learning experience tailored to their individual needs. It therefore instills a sense of autonomy in the students with total control over their learning process and helps them to build confidence in grappling hard mathematical concepts. Teachers can monitor how students are progressing through Edpuzzle's analytics, which will provide detailed information about the level of engagement, as well as performance and achievement in quizzes and areas that students find difficult. Such instant feedback empowers teachers to act immediately and then focus their support on the struggling students.

This online intervention program will indeed yield some impressive results. First, one would expect the students to exhibit a marked improvement in knowledge and mastery of the least learned competencies and track this progress through pre- and post-intervention assessments. Second, engaging interactive video lessons are expected to motivate the students to learn, thereby making the mathematics learning process enjoyable while reducing anxiety around the more troublesome topics. With this new approach, teachers will have access to detailed data regarding the students' improvement, which will further enable them to alter instructions given and customized feedback.

There will be three plans for the implementation of the program. First will be the preparation and planning phase: where teachers will be undergoing professional development to familiarize them with Edpuzzle's specific features and interaction with content that should be produced, along with the process of tracking the student progress. During the validation stage, mathematics teachers will collaborate to develop video lessons that are constructed based on the standard curriculum. These video lessons will be emphasized the least learned competencies. The pilot roll-out and delivery of the program will be executed with a small number of participants to test the effectiveness of the program as well as gather feedback regarding such training. Based on the results of the pilot, the full roll-out of the program will be done in participating classes. Finally, there would be an administration of post-assessment of intervention impact on students' learning outcomes. The findings will then help modify the program to prepare for future improvements in it.

The costs that would be involved in the program are subscriptions to Edpuzzle Pro, teacher training, and resources for developing video lessons in a suitable and high-quality form. In the long term, this would provide a sustainable and scalable model that may be used in several schools at different grade levels, addressing the gaps in learning mathematics.

The online intervention program offers a timely and innovative way of addressing the least learned competencies in mathematics. Edpuzzle: This tool has incorporated interactive features that keep students actively engaged with the content of learning, give them instant feedback, and control their learning. Simultaneously, teachers are empowered by using data-driven insights for targeted support. The intervention in mathematics education improves student outcomes thus providing a vital opportunity for schools to continue closing those persistent gaps in the core subjects.

Conclusions

In light of the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed for improving teaching and learning mathematics, in particular concerning least learned competencies among Grade 8 students through online intervention, such as Edpuzzle. Some recommendations include the adoption of interactive video-based learning tools in schools as part of mathematics instructional strategy. This study therefore showcased how these tools work to engage the learner and fill specific gaps that may have resulted from their learning process. Incorporation of interactive videos into a learning curriculum can help personalize learning to be dynamic and engaging, especially with complicated topics.

Professional training for teachers would also come in handy regarding successful implementation. Schools should hold workshop sessions utilizing Edpuzzle and other such applications, content preparation or video editing as well as analytics regarding the monitoring of student improvement. Once teachers acquire such abilities, they will then be better placed to enhance the quality of instruction but also reap fully the full benefits of these tools.

Third, targeted interventions by schools must be of concern. Most importantly, specific diagnostics-asserted least learned competencies need to be identified through diagnostic assessments. Targeted intervention toward those specific gaps may lead to improved outcomes of learning; Edpuzzle is being used to suggest such targeted instruction so that students can engage with content that directly addresses their areas of difficulty.

Furthermore, remediation should be done in a system of online intervention, particularly concerning remedial instructions to students with a need for improvement in core mathematics. Such as the learning characteristics of flexibility, learning ability at one's own pace, reviewing difficult topics, and receiving immediate feedback within Edpuzzle are what make it most suitable for remediation purposes. Particularly beneficial among remote or hybrid learners in areas wherein access to teachers is a challenge.

Moreover, through the analytics tools of Edpuzzle, there should be constant student monitoring and assessment to know if they continue to have problems in their competencies that they have had no success in mastering previously. This data-informed way will enable a teacher to pick out a student who still needs support in his/her competencies by the provision of just-in-time support. Continuous checking of students ensures that data-based decision-making guides instruction.

In addition, the research also suggested that interactive tools such as Edpuzzle must not be applied specifically to mathematics only.

Since the intervention has proven to be successful in this subject, similar interventions can be applied to other subjects such as science, English and social studies. Hence, students may need to have more interesting and personalized learning experiences in all these subjects. In all these subjects, otherwise, the comprehensive usage of such tools may bring about significant developments in the levels of engagement and achievement among students.

It is on this recommendation that a blended approach to teaching, which integrates instructor-initiated in-class instruction with online tools such as Edpuzzle, is recommended. Its online feature makes it suited to use both in-class and remote learning environments; hence, delivering to students the opportunity of flexible learning approaches made possible with student needs in mind. This may be very handy during times of class suspensions due to weather conditions but requires the children to continue to learn.

Finally, it would be worth more studies on the long-term effects of these interactive video-based learning tools, such as Edpuzzle, on mathematics student outcomes. Longitudinal studies can help find more insights regarding the influence of such tools on students' mastery of competencies in the long run and various learning contexts. The impact of such interventions over the long term is crucial to refining and maintaining improvements in student outcomes.

These sets of proposals can hence guide how school practices would be improved in order to make mathematics education more appealing, interactive, and effective for the specific students' needs and general student performance.

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